

EPPO DIAGNOSTIC PROTOCOL ON XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA, CONTRIBUTION OF XF-ACTORS & PONTE

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The first EPPO diagnostic protocol on *Xylella fastidiosa* was adopted in 2004. The first revision was adopted in September 2016 and took into account the experience gained by different laboratories after the *Xylella fastidiosa* outbreak in Europe. A second revision was adopted in April 2018. The diagnostic protocol was published on the EPPO Bulletin and is available on <https://gd.eppo.int/download/standard/148/pm7-024-3-en.pdf>. This recent version takes into account the outcomes of different projects and in particular an interlaboratory comparison performed in the framework of POnTE, XF-ACTORS and a Euphresco project. The EPPO Secretariat is in close contact with the researchers involved in the different projects and the next revision is already planned and a first Exert Working Group was organized in September 2018. The revisions envisaged for the next version of the protocol will be presented highlighting how outcomes of the different research projects can assist with a timely update of the diagnostic protocol.